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D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

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Author(s):	Esteban Gonzalez (UPM), Daniel Garijo (UPM), Raul Palma (PSNC), Barbara Magagna (GFF), Milos Ulman (P4A), Cristian Berrío (Expert.AI), Despina-Athanasia Pantazi (NKUA), Elianna DeSota (DesCi)
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Terms and Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
3PFF	Three-Point FAIRification Framework
FAIRification	Process of applying FAIR principles to digital objects
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
RO	Research Object
RO-Crate	Lightweight, JSON-LD based specification for packaging research objects and their metadata
WP	Work Package
PID	Persistent Identifier
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
DO	Digital Object
CS	Case Study
RSFC	Research Software FAIRness Checks
FSR	FAIR Supporting Resource
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud

Executive Summary

One of the objectives of the FAIR2Adapt project is to improve the accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of climate adaptation knowledge by applying the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles to digital objects, resulting in FAIR Digital Objects. While the FAIR principles provide a strong conceptual framework for data sharing, their practical implementation remains challenging due to the multiple possible implementation approaches and the level of technical expertise required. Furthermore, their application to other types of digital objects, such as software, workflows, and publications, is not always clear.

This deliverable presents the FAIRification Framework developed within FAIR2Adapt, adapted to the climate change adaptation domain. The framework builds on existing FAIRification approaches, in particular the Three Point FAIRification Framework (3PFF), and extends them by reducing human intervention through the orchestration of multiple FAIR enabling services available within the project. Its objective is to support communities, represented by different case studies, in transforming digital resources into machine-actionable, interoperable, and reusable FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) with reduced manual effort.

This deliverable reviews existing technical approaches for implementing FAIR Digital Objects, with particular attention to nanopublications and RO-Crates. Based on this analysis, FAIR2Adapt adopts RO-Crates, extended through community specific profiles, as the primary mechanism for implementing FDOs. In addition, nanopublications will be used to add complementary information to the profiles, such as scientific hypotheses, claims, and related assertions.

The core of this deliverable describes the FAIR2Adapt FAIRification Framework, including its lifecycle methodology based on the software lifecycle, and the set of FAIR enabling services that support FAIR assessment, metadata extraction, semantic enrichment, knowledge representation, and publication. The interactions between these services are described in a FAIRification Plan, which is implemented through a FAIRification pipeline. This pipeline orchestrates the execution of the services and is designed to be adaptable to different types of resources and community needs.

Finally, the deliverable outlines the implementation of the framework across the FAIR2Adapt case studies, demonstrating how FAIR Implementation Plans are derived from community requirements and executed using the proposed services.

1. Introduction

The **FAIR Data principles** represented a major shift in how researchers should publish their data. They provided a set of high-level principles intended to improve data sharing and re-use. However, although an important starting point, the FAIR principles have two main limitations: (i) they are **not very concrete**, they primarily describe *requirements*, and (ii) most **researchers do not have the expertise** to operationalise them, because FAIR touches many different aspects: metadata, semantic artefacts, licences, persistent identifiers (PIDs), etc.

As a result, there is a clear need for **practical, structured, and partially automated FAIRification guidance**. Existing frameworks, such as the FAIR Cookbook, provide valuable step-by-step methodologies but typically rely heavily on manual processes and expert supervision throughout the lifecycle. This deliverable presents the **FAIRification Framework developed within the FAIR2Adapt project**, adapted to the climate change adaptation domain. The framework builds on existing FAIRification approaches, in particular the Three-Point FAIRification Framework (3PFF), and adapts them to support the systematic transformation of heterogeneous research outputs, such as data, software, and publications, into **FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)**.

The proposed framework has three specific characteristics: (i) it produces FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs), (ii) it orchestrates multiple services to produce the FDO, and (iii) it automates the majority of the FAIRification pipeline.

This deliverable builds upon and complements other FAIR2Adapt documents. In particular, it is closely aligned with **Deliverable D5.2**, which focuses on requirements elicitation and defines a methodology for identifying requirements across the project's case studies. The outcomes of D5.2, such as the digital objects involved in the CS, serve as direct inputs to the FAIRification Framework described here.

Section 2 describes the foundations upon which the FAIRification Framework is built. It analyzes the 3PFF Framework, the requirements elicitation process, and the different approaches to implementing FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) and creating profiles, with a focus on the solution adopted by the project.

Section 3 describes the methodology of the FAIR2Adapt FAIRification Framework in detail, presenting its phases from the requirements elicitation, to the creation of the FDO.

Section 4 describes the services that support the FAIRification process. This section explains how these services cover the FAIR principles and how they can interact to enable the creation, enrichment, assessment, and publication of FAIR Digital Objects.

Section 5 presents the implementation of the methodology across the FAIR2Adapt case studies. For each case study, it outlines the FAIRification Plan that can be executed to FAIRify its resources.

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Section 6 summarises the main conclusions of the deliverable and outlines the next steps for the FAIRification Framework, including its validation through demonstrators and its evolution based on feedback from the project's communities.

2. Foundations

Based on the FAIR Hourglass concept [1], the FAIR2Adapt project develops a FAIRification Framework to turn data into actionable knowledge to shape climate adaptation strategies.

Fig. 1 FAIR2Adapt WP Distribution

The hourglass shape (Fig. 1) represents the flexibility at both the beginning and end of the process:

- The upper part focuses on FAIRifying community-provided data.
- The lower part ensures FAIR Orchestration, enabling services to act on FAIR-ready data.
- At the center, the FAIR Digital Object (FDO) ensures machine readability and interoperable reuse of digital objects. Our approach is based on RO-Crates, used as a container of FDOs, Nanopublications, to express knowledge inside the FDO and aligned with DTR.

2.1 The Three-point FAIRification Framework (3PFF)

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The following framework is related to the creation of Fair Digital Objects (FDOs). This framework is proposed by the GO FAIR foundation and it will be the base of our framework, as indicated in the project's proposal.

The Three-Point FAIRification Framework is a guideline/roadmap developed by the GO FAIR community to help organizations, data producers, research communities, etc. *go FAIR* — i.e. make their data and services Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (especially for machines).

The goal is to provide **practical** and **coordinated** steps so that FAIRification is doable, not just aspirational. It helps stakeholders understand what concrete actions to take, in what order, what trade-offs are involved, so that FAIR principles are not just ideals but get embedded in data systems, metadata, infrastructure, etc.

The framework aims to maximize reuse of existing resources, accelerate convergence on standards/technologies, and improve interoperability across communities.

The 3PFF consists of three interrelated components or "decision-points" (sometimes called "points" in the framework), each with its own focus. They are:

1. **FIP — FAIR Implementation Profile**

- A FAIR Implementation Profile is basically a published description of what metadata standards, vocabulary, data policy, etc., a community (or domain) considers necessary for FAIR in that domain. So it is not "one size fits all," but what a given domain or community agrees is relevant.
- The FIP helps communities make consistent, interoperable choices. When a community has a FIP, others know what schemas, metadata fields, etc. to expect or to align with.

2. **M4M — Metadata for Machines / Machine-Actionable Metadata**

- This is about defining metadata (and associated vocabularies, policies, etc.) in a way that machines can process: so metadata components are explicit, standardised, formalised, with clear semantics, etc.
- Often done via workshops ("Metadata for Machines" Workshops) where stakeholders decide on metadata requirements, what schemata to use, how to make metadata machine-actionable.

3. **FO — FAIR Orchestration** (sometimes referred to as FAIR Data Points / FAIR infrastructure in earlier versions)

- This concerns the infrastructure and operational deployment: how to implement FAIR in practice: which technologies, what infrastructure, how data/repositories are made FAIR, how they support findability, access, etc.
- It includes specific components such as FAIR Data Points (FDPs), FAIR Digital Objects, tools/portals, and decisions around configuration and operations that align with the FIP.

In order to be applied to our project, we identified the following challenges:

- Preparing all the material and standards require a lot of effort

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- It involves a high number of steps that needs to do it upon supervision of experts in the framework

This framework constitutes the foundation upon which the FAIR2Adapt framework is built.

2.2 FAIRification Requirements

Deliverable D5.2 focuses on requirements elicitation, a pre-phase of the FAIRification process that aims to identify the specific needs of stakeholders. This deliverable proposes a methodology for extracting the requirements of the different case studies, including those related to FAIRification.

The following figure (extracted from D5.2) depicts the requirements process.

Fig. 2: Processing phases in the requirement elicitation process

As can be seen, there is a phase, Digital Object Analysis, associated with the FAIRification process. In this phase, the digital objects of each case study are identified. This phase serves as the entry point to the FAIRification Framework, which is responsible for generating a FAIRification Plan that can ultimately be executed by humans and machines to produce the FDOs.

2.3 FDO Profiles

In FAIR2Adapt, we will create a collection of profiles to support the implementation of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). This section describes the different approaches that can be used to implement FDOs and explains the option selected by the project, including how it aligns with the project's objectives. Finally, we will explore how this solution can interoperate with the Data Green Data Space.

2.3.1 Nanopublications

A nanopublication is a small knowledge graph configured according to a specification¹, with the purpose to provide statements about anything as an independent publication. Nanopublications are expressed using knowledge representation languages, allowing machine-interpretations. They can be represented as RDF in TriG notation or N-Quads, JSON-LD or XML. They follow a general structure with these elements:

Fig 3. Nanopublication Structure

1. Assertion: The assertion is the main content of a nanopublication in the form of a small atomic unit of information, involving one or more triple statements.
2. Provenance: This part describes how the assertion above came to be. This can include the scientific methods that were used to generate the assertion, for example a reference to the kind of study that was performed and its parameters.
3. Publication Info: This part contains metadata about the nanopublication as a whole, such as when and by whom it was created and the license terms for its reuse.

¹ https://nanopub.net/guidelines/working_draft/

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They can be published to a decentralized server network and then queried, accessed, reused, and linked.

While nanopublications were originally conceived to have a single RDF statement in the assertion to express a fact, observation or hypothesis [2], this paradigm has shifted towards a more general approach that allows for multiple RDF triples in order to express more complex statements. Furthermore, since their original conception, nanopublications have been broadened in their scope of use, to cover not only scientific statements, but also data points and datasets, workflows, social relations, reviews, annotations, and in general, all kinds of statements on the domain, meta, and social levels.

Furthermore, nanopublications can be used to make objects FAIR by providing formally precise statements about their nature and contexts. The nanopublication network provides stable and persistent identifiers for the addressed objects but also for nanopublications serving as their metadata records.

Based on the analysis [3], it is proved that nanopublications, when properly configured, are consistent with the FAIR Digital Objects requirements. They can be typed according to an agreed typology, their profile defined and registered in a FAIR registry and they can be referenced by their trust-URIs.

2.3.2 RO crates

RO-Crate is an open, community driven specification for describing Research Objects, which researchers can use to package all the resources used and generated throughout the research process such as datasets, publications, software, and other resources. The current version available for adoption is 1.2.

The research object container and its aggregated resources are semantically described with rich metadata, expressed in JSON-LD following a Linked Data approach, in a file named **ro-crate-metadata.json**. The metadata is based on common and well-known vocabularies, mainly in Schema.org, and it can be easily extended and profiled through the specification of RO-Crate profiles, which can leverage different metadata standards. This file, together with the research resources, can be packaged into a ZIP archive for sharing (known as an attached RO-Crate package), or it can be provided as a stand-alone RO-Crate metadata document stored in a file or distributed via an API (known as a detached RO-Crate package). Packaging the resources is not mandatory; they may also be referenced via a URI in the metadata file (called Web-based data entity). RO-Crates would typically have a persistent identifier (PID), such as DOI or W3ID, and thus they can be referenced and cited. In short, they are self-described (the metadata lives inside the crate), extensible (can describe different types of resources and support profiling), and portable (can be zipped, published, or deposited in repositories)

The metadata file is composed of

- a self-describing **RO-Crate Metadata Descriptor**, with a type schema:CreativeWork, and and schema:about property referencing the Root Data Entity's @id.

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- the **Root Data Entity** describing the RO-Crate itself (referenced in the metadata descriptor), with type `schema:Dataset.zero` or more **Data Entities**, representing the aggregated resources as files and folders, and their metadata such as name, description, authors, and more. These entities should be identified via an absolute URI (Web-based data entity) or relative URIs.
- zero or more **Contextual Entities**, which describe additional information related to the Research Object, such as people, organizations, locations, funding, and property rights, providing for example provenance about the RO-Crate and data entities. These entities are preferably identified via existing PIDs or absolute URI, such as ORCID for people, ROR id for organizations, etc.

Below is a high-level view of an (attached) RO-Crate package, which include various contextual entities like authors (identified by ORCID), organizations (identified by ROR), and license (identified by CC URL), as well as various data entities including folders and files (both Web-based and inside the package)

Fig 4. RO-Crate structure

Below is a simplified example of a RO-Crate metadata file that can be found on the ROHUB platform.

```

{
  "@context": [
    "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context",
    "https://w3id.org/ro/terms/earth-science#",
    ...],
  "@graph": [
    {
      "@id": "./",
      "@type": [
        "Dataset",
        "http://purl.org/wf4ever/ro#ResearchObject",
        "http://purl.org/wf4ever/roevo#LiveRO" ],
      "about": [
        {
          "@id": "http://eurovoc.europa.eu/3949"
        },
        ... ],
      "author": [
        {
          "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2104-3187"
        },
        {
          "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8796-5993"
        }
      ],
      "contentSize": 1364570,
      "contentUrl":
        "https://api.rohub.org/api/ros/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94/crate/download/",
      "creator": {
        "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2104-3187"
      },
      "dateCreated": "2025-10-13 11:12:49.327063+00:00",
      "dateModified": "2025-10-20 13:33:34.491167+00:00",
      "datePublished": "2025-10-13 11:12:49.327063+00:00",
      "description": "Presentation at the CE3C Annual Meeting, Azores - Portugal\n\n*10-12 October
2025*\n\nThe first Portuguese National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change was adopted in 2010,
aiming to adjust climate and other sectoral policies, and to increase the countries\u2019 resilience to
observed and projected climate change impacts. ... This work was developed under the Horizon Europe
project FAIR2Adapt.",
      "encodingFormat": "application/ld+json",
      "hasPart": [
        {
          "@id":
            "https://w3id.org/ro-id/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94/resources/ebc84d30-9700-471e-ae2f-
d04486f18c8d"
        },
        {
          "@id":
            "https://w3id.org/ro-id/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94/resources/b1a0d3cc-179c-4077-9d29-
f14b8bada1d7"
        },
        {
          "@id":
            "https://w3id.org/ro-id/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94/resources/a6c04f4c-0a9f-4b8d-8492-9
6a06dba7808"
        }
      ],
      "identifier": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94",
      "keywords": [
        "climate change",
        "FAIR",
        "heat" ],
      "license": {
        "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode"
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

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```
    },
    "name": "Facing heat extremes: lessons learned from 15 years of climate change adaptation in
Portugal",
    "publisher": {
      "@id": "https://www.ce3c.pt/"
    },
    "enrichmentSubject": [
      {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/enrichment/09480284-f698-4259-a0ca-49185a50d5b9"
      },
      {
        "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/enrichment/0ad5b37d-6963-49e5-8d0c-b05e65c334f2"
      },
      ... ]
    ... },
  {
    "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2104-3187",
    "@type": "foaf:Agent",
    "affiliation": "Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes, University of Lisbon",
    "email": "igmarques@fc.ul.pt",
    "name": "Ines Gomes Marques",
    "orcid": "0000-0002-2104-3187"
  }
  ...
  {
    "@id": "http://eurovoc.europa.eu/3949",
    "@type": [
      "s:DefinedTerm",
      "DefinedTerm"],
    "description": "",
    "name": "Applied sciences"
  },
  ...
  {
    "@id": "https://w3id.org/ro-id/enrichment/09480284-f698-4259-a0ca-49185a50d5b9",
    "@type": "Concept",
    "name": "Portugal",
    "normScore": "14.640522875816993",
    "score": "11.2"
  }
  ...
  {
    "@id":
"https://w3id.org/ro-id/416a0645-07b8-4c30-99be-a80481dab614/resources/046b8c59-bbbf-4a38-ae80-
1135d5e267f4",
    "@type": [
      "File",
      "http://purl.org/wf4ever/wf4ever#Resource",
      "PresentationDigitalDocument" ],
    "doi": "10.24424/xq9z-p873",
    "author": { "@id": "https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2104-3187" },
    "contentSize": 1057305,
    "contentUrl":
"https://api.rohub.org/api/resources/046b8c59-bbbf-4a38-ae80-1135d5e267f4/download/",
    "creator": {
      "@id": "0000-0002-2104-3187"
    },
    "dateCreated": "2025-10-13 11:48:29.771773+00:00",
    "dateModified": "2025-11-13 12:51:59.085534+00:00",
    "encodingFormat": "application/pdf",
    "license": { "@id": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode" },
    "name": "Facing heat extremes: lessons learned from 15 years of climate change adaptation in
Portugal",
```

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```
"sdDatePublished": "2025-10-13 11:48:29.771773+00:00"  
},  
...  
}
```

We can differentiate two parts: the **context** and the **graph**. The context introduces the vocabularies that will be used in the RO-Crate. This is an important feature that we will address later when discussing RO-Crate profiles.

The graph contains the different resources that make up an RO-Crate, including RO-Crate metadata descriptor, the root data entity, the data entities and the contextual entities, as described above.

A complete example of the content can be found at the following link: <https://w3id.org/ro-id/302b4ebf-db38-49d5-8ab4-4561181f4e94>

Up to this point, we have been talking about the Research Object, but what is its connection with the FAIR Digital Object? This will be addressed in Section 2.3.4.

2.3.3 FDO Connect

The FDO Connect project²³ developed a framework for FDOs that is a proposed unification of Handle-based FDOs with those represented in RDF, such as nanopublications but also RO-Crates. It turned out that these different kinds of FDOs differed not only in their technology but also in their conceptual models. The project succeeded in unifying both, the model as well as the technological layer.

FDOs in general are thought to be able to change over time, so the same FDO identifier can stand for a different digital representation at different points in time, corresponding to different versions of the given FDOs. And the same holds for an FDO's metadata record, which can adapt to the changes the FDO undergoes. This change has been possible in Handle-based FDOs, but was not until now properly represented, as the different versions had no identifiers and there were no version control mechanisms in place. On the other hand, FDOs that use nanopublications for their metadata records automatically get strong persistent identifiers for each version of a metadata record, but there is not a clear scheme or mechanism to align such version identifiers with the permanent identifiers of a changing FDO itself.

FDO Connect has now put forward a simple bi-directional mapping of how FDO metadata records can be turned into nanopublications, while keeping all identifiers intact. Apart from allowing FDOs to live in both spaces, this gives the Handle-based FDOs a well-defined method for version control and makes nanopublication-based ones aligned with general FDO identifier expectations.

² <https://w3id.org/spaces/fdo-connect>

³ <https://www.dfki.de/en/web/research/projects-and-publications/project/fdo-connect>

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Building on top of this basis, FDO Connect defined how FDO Profiles and the related FDO Attributes can be described and used within and across these systems, laying the basis for a general cross-platform and cross-implementation conceptual alignment of FDOs. Even though not the focus of the project, this alignment was made considering also the RO-Crate approach, and adopted its use of `dcterms:conformsTo` for linking FDOs to their profiles. This simple link between a given FDO and its profile expressed as a well-defined RDF-based statement can now serve as a practical entry point for aligning all the major kinds of currently used FDOs: Handle-based, nanopublication-based, as well as RO-Crate-based ones.

2.3.4 FAIR2Adapt FDO specification (RO crates profiles)

According to this study [4], RO-Crates can be used to model lightweight FDOs. As described in Section 2.3.2, an RO-Crate can serve as a container that semantically describes the various resources involved in research. Note that a Research Object can consist of only a single resource, such as a dataset, if needed.

As described in the specification, while RO-Crates can be considered general-purpose containers of arbitrary data and open-ended metadata, in practical use within a particular domain (like climate change adaptation), application or framework, it will be generally beneficial to further constrain RO-Crate to a specific profile: a set of conventions, types and properties that one can minimally require and expect to be present in that subset of RO-Crates.

This mechanism will be adopted in FAIR2Adapt. One challenge in FAIR2Adapt is the need to use community-specific metadata for each case study represented in the project. This will be addressed by creating an RO-Crate profile for the climate change adaptation community, or if needed, individual RO-Crate profiles for each community during the course of the project. These profiles can be understood as extensions to the RO-Crate specification, and they will be integrated into the context section of the RO-Crate metadata file.

Defining and conforming to such a profile enables reliable programmatic consumption of an RO-Crate's content, a consistent creation, e.g. via a form in a user interface containing the required types and properties, or an easier creation of rich UI components for the rendering of an RO-Crate.

The RO-Crate profile(s) will be identified with a profile URI, which should be persistent (PID), versioned and resolve to a human-readable profile description (e.g., HTML web page), and optionally a corresponding machine-readable Profile Crate. The Profile Crate is a type of RO-Crate that represents an RO-Crate profile. It gathers resources which further define the profile in addition to the profile description.

The Profile Crate may include a list of profile resource descriptors, which have associated the role within the crate. There are various predefined roles, including constraints, validation, specification and vocabulary. For example the specification defines the profile in human-readable form, the vocabulary defines the terms used in the profile specification (in

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an ontology), and the validation supplies instructions about how to verify conformance of data to the profile (e.g., using SHACL).

Hence, to facilitate this integration, a collection of SHACL files will be created to verify the validity of RO-Crates instantiated with the newly defined profiles.

Based on this approach, the FDOs in FAIR2Adapt will be created using the RO-Crate specification, extended with community-specific requirements (RO-Crate profiles).

But, how interoperable is this solution with other EOSC services? Can these FDOs be integrated in a Data Space? We will answer this question in the next section.

2.3.5 Interoperability with Green Deal Data space

The European Strategy for Data (2020) sets the direction for sectoral common European data spaces (often referenced as “~14 data spaces”) as a core instrument to enable trusted cross-border data sharing and a stronger EU data economy. The Common European data spaces policy stream (governance + infrastructure “design principles”, funding and coordination) sits under the EU digital/data strategy from the European Commission, and is supported by the data governance act (2022/868) and data act (2023/2854), which address the concepts of trust framework (data sharing, reuse of public-sector data, data intermediaries, data altruism), and Fair access/use of data and interoperability, respectively. The green deal data space (GDDS) is one of the sectorial common European data spaces framed by the Commission as an initiative to leverage data for EU environmental and climate policies (Green Deal implementation needs: observation data, interoperable sharing, reuse).

The project SAGE (<https://www.greendealdata.eu/>) has been funded to implement it. In particular, SAGE will establish a fully operational Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) aimed at enhancing the accessibility, integration, and utilization of green and environmental data across the EU to support key pillars of the European Green Deal, including Zero Pollution, Climate Adaptation, Biodiversity, and Circular Economy Action Plan. SAGE’s outcomes include seamlessly integrating fragmented environmental data through federation, enriching data with consistent quality, validation, and interoperable metadata, and enhancing capabilities for data transformation, processing, analysis, forecasting, target setting, and performance monitoring. SAGE has released its first architecture deliverable, which describes the main components envisioned for the implementation of the data space. One of the key technologies to realize the data space are the connectors (e.g., from Eclipse Data Components), which implement the IDSA data space protocol (DSP) and recommendations from DSSC (Data Space Support Center). SAGE is leveraging results from previous projects, like AD4GD, which include operational and extended EDC connectors, common data models (ontologies), vocabularies (e.g., essential variables) and metadata schemas, and data harmonization components.

The GDDS will provide access to a variety of data assets and resources (e.g., services) that can provide value to different stakeholders. In the case of FAIR2Adapt, it will be potentially able to benefit from it, allowing not only to find and consume assets and other resources, but

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also to publish assets produced in the project to a wider audience. Moreover, one of the key benefits of data spaces is the provision of a control layer enabling a secure and trustworthy data exchange, where data governance is ensured. This is realized, for example, via the definition of data access and reuse policies, which are formally specified (e.g., using ODRL ontology), and enforced by the connectors. Hence, data providers and pilot stakeholders in FAIR2Adapt will be able to define clear rules for sharing and the reuse of their data. In a next phase, this could also be complemented with economical benefits, e.g., providing access only after some payment, or in exchange of other services/assets.

3. Methodology

FAIR2Adapt has designed a methodology to FAIRify the available digital objects in order to transform the resources of the Climate Adaptation Community, represented by the case studies, into FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). The approach follows a lifecycle similar to the Software Development Lifecycle and is composed of the following phases: (i) problem analysis, (ii) solution design, (iii) solution implementation, and (iv) testing.

The first phase corresponds to the analysis of the resources. This phase is connected to the process defined in Section 2.2, which aims to identify the requirements related to the specific case studies. The following picture depicted the resources and steps involved.

Fig 5. Analysis phase

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This phase involves a community-driven process for developing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices. As described in D5.2, communities use the FIP Wizard to execute the requirements elicitation process. This includes describing their case studies (challenges and goals), formulating user stories, identifying the digital objects involved, and conducting digital object analysis. In parallel, FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) are developed by technical experts together with communities to specify the FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs) relevant to particular types of digital objects. These FIPs are designed to be reusable: once established, they can serve as inputs for other end-users who wish to FAIRify their own data, software, workflows, or other digital objects following the same community standards. Based on the FIPs and FAIR assessments, FAIRification Plans are derived that guide subsequent actions in the FAIR data ecosystem. Based on the outputs of this “Analysis Phase”, and particularly the metadata schemas and standards identified in the FIPs, FAIR2Adapt will identify gaps in existing metadata “coverage”. To address these gaps, M4M workshops will be conducted with community stakeholders to define the additional metadata requirements needed to make digital objects machine-actionable. The outcomes of these workshops, combined with the standards identified in the FIPs, will inform the creation of RO-Crate profiles. These profiles will be used to describe the resources included in the FDO, according to the specific needs of the case studies, mainly the metadata needed for these case studies. One example of these RO-Crates can be found in M2.1

As a secondary outcome, and also derived from the requirements, a collection of metrics will be defined to assess the FAIRness of the previously identified resources. This initial assessment will help identify which FAIR principles are not adequately addressed by the resources. This information will be crucial for deciding which services can be used to improve compliance with these FAIR principles. A complete list of services can be found in section 4.

All this information (the FIPs, RO-Crate profiles, identified digital objects, and FAIR assessment metrics) serve as inputs to the next phase: the design phase. The following figure 6 depicts this phase.

Fig 6. Design phase

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This phase is responsible for defining a FAIRification Plan, a document that outlines the steps needed to create an FDO. It includes the generation of PIDs, the creation of mappings to align specific metadata schemas with the Ro-Crate profiles created, and other relevant tasks. A version of these documents can be found in Section 5, where we describe the steps needed to FAIRify the resources of each case study.

This plan will be developed based on the FAIR assessment conducted in the previous phase, using the metrics defined during that same phase. A catalog of these metrics can be found in the FAIROs catalog⁴. FAIROs is the tool that we will use to assess the FAIRness of FDOs.

Once the FAIRification Plan is defined, it can be executed in the implementation phase. Figure 7 depicts this phase.

Fig 7. Implementation phase

The objective of this implementation is to create a FDO following the FAIRification plan designed in the previous phase. During this phase, the FDO is enriched with additional metadata extracted by multiple enrichment services, resulting in a fully enriched FDO. A complete list of these services and their purposes can be found in section 4.

The final step covers testing and deployment, and is depicted in Figure 8. During testing, the FDO is validated to ensure it meets the FAIR metrics defined by the community. The same FAIR Assessment tool used in the analysis phase is applied here, ensuring methodological consistency throughout the FAIRification process. Additionally, the RO-Crates are validated against the defined profiles. Once validated, the FDO is published through the deployment pipeline and made available to researchers

⁴ <http://w3id.org/FAIROS/catalog>

Fig 8. Testing and Deployment phase

4. Services

The FAIRification Framework is composed of various services used to create enriched FDOs. These services are integrated within the FAIRification Framework but can also be used independently of it.

In this section, the reader will find a brief description of each service involved, along with the endpoint for each service.

The following figure 9 depicts the interaction of the different services present in the framework

Fig 9. Services interaction in the FAIRification process

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The process begins with the **FIP** Wizard service, which is used to identify the community's FAIR implementation strategy. It draws from three key types of resources:

- **Metrics:** FAIRness criteria that help evaluate the FAIRness of digital objects.
- **Digital Objects:** The digital objects identified by the communities and must be fairified.
- **FAIR Supporting Resources:** Tools or standards that support the implementation of FAIR principles.

Digital Objects are assessed using the provided **Metrics** and *FAIR Supporting Resources* by the FAIR Assessment service. This tool identifies both strengths and gaps in the object's FAIR compliance.

Based on the FAIR Assessment, a customized **FAIR Implementation Plan** is created. This plan outlines necessary actions and steps to improve the FAIRness of the digital object. This plan includes the support and enrichment services needed.

The FAIR Implementation Plan is supported by two types of services:

- Support Services
- Enrichment Services

Support Services_

- **Pythia Question Answering Engine:** This service provides a natural language interface to knowledge graphs, thus providing improved accessibility to both novice and expert users.
- **ToposKG:** The methodology and accompanying datasets that is ToposKG enables the integration of high quality and topologically sound geospatial data for administrative divisions world-wide.
- **ORKG Reborn:** The service provides a digital infrastructure to make scientific knowledge reusable. It breaks down research into granular statements rather than keeping it locked in static papers, providing research outcomes together with the evidence that created them.
- **JackDaw LLM integrating GI services:** The service supports metadata extraction through natural language querying, field mapping, and eventually adaptive metadata generation.
- **Metadata catalogue for geospatial data:** The service will be integrated through a wrapper to allow for interoperable sharing and publishing of geospatial datasets especially in case study 2 (RioMar) and case study 3 (Hamburg).

Enrichment Services_

- **Metadata Extraction:** The service will be integrated in ROHub. This service extracts relevant information from text as metadata such as topics, keywords, time, coordinates, etc.

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- **Scientific Claims Extraction and Verification.** This service will extract claims from scientific publications. Although it will be integrated in RoHub, the FAIRification Framework will use it to create machine-actionable publications in ORKG Reborn.
- **Automated I-ADOPT service:** These services enhance and enrich digital content, making it more structured and machine-actionable.

Once enriched, digital objects can be published through three complementary platforms:

- **ROHUB** for managing the enriched digital objects via RO-Crates: Serves as both a collaborative workspace and a repository. During the FAIRification process, researchers use ROHub to create, edit, and enrich FDOs collaboratively, with support for versioning and lifecycle management. Once complete, FDOs can be published, shared, and discovered through the same platform. ROHub is the default environment for FDO development and publication in the project.
- **ORKG (Open Research Knowledge Graph)** for managing enriched papers: Enables structured, machine-readable descriptions of research contributions, primarily scientific papers and their findings. ORKG can export these descriptions as RO-Crates, which can then be integrated into ROHub.
- **DeSci publish:** A decentralised publishing platform built on IPFS (Inter-Planetary File System) that assigns persistent identifiers and automatically generates RO-Crates. It supports publishing metadata while keeping underlying data private or access-controlled: it is particularly useful for cases where data can only be shared for specific purposes (e.g., restricted socio-economic data in Case Study 3).

The following subsections describe each service involved in the FAIRification process, categorised according to the FAIR Supporting Resource Typology (Figure 10). In future steps of the FAIRification Framework, the services will be catalogued as FAIR Supporting Resources (FSRs). This will make them discoverable by other frameworks and FAIRification processes and will help increase the automation of those processes.

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Fig 10. FAIR Supporting Resource Typology

4.1 FAIR Assessment

Description

The FAIR Assessment service is based in the tool FAIROs⁵. Originally, FAIROs was conceived as a tool to assess the FAIRness of Research Objects. In the context of FAIR2Adapt, it is being adapted to evaluate FDOs. FDOs present certain particularities, as they are composed of digital objects of different natures (datasets, software, ontologies), which require different approaches for assessment. To address this, FAIROs uses external tools such as F-UJI[5] and RSFC⁶, and adapts their outputs to the specific characteristics of each Digital Object.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service will assess the FAIRness of Digital Objects within the Climate Adaptation community. The metrics used will be defined collaboratively by the Climate Adaptation community (through the FAIR2Adapt case studies) and by FAIRness experts involved in the project.

The tool is used at two points in the FAIRification Framework: first, during the analysis phase to identify which FAIR principles are not adequately addressed and inform the FAIRification

⁵ <https://w3id.org/FAIROs>

⁶ <https://github.com/oeg-upm/rsfc>

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Plan; and second, during the testing phase to validate that the final FDO meets the community-defined metrics.

Input / Outputs

Input: url/pid of a Digital Object Output: a JSON file with the results of the assessment, based on the specification defined [here](#)

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be found [here](#)

FAIR Principles coverage

Because this tool is used solely to assess the FAIRness of a Research Object, it does not provide a means to address any of the FAIR principles.

Metadata provided

No metadata is provided.

4.2 Automated I-ADOPT service

Description

I-ADOPT (InteroperAble Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology) is a framework for describing observable properties and variables in a standardised, machine-actionable way. It decomposes complex variable descriptions into structured components: the Property being measured, the ObjectOfInterest being observed, and optional constraints such as the Matrix (the environmental context) and ContextObject (additional qualifying conditions).

The Automated I-ADOPT service applies this framework to digital objects by analysing textual descriptions of scientific variables and generating structured, semantically enriched representations. This semi-automated approach reduces the manual effort typically required

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to create interoperable variable descriptions while ensuring consistency across datasets and case studies.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service allows adding semantic context focused on the research variable to the digital objects in a structured semi-automatic way and enables multi-faceted search in RoHub.

This service will make metadata and data FAIR by defining what they represent.

Input / Outputs

Input: text with the description about the scientific observables.

Output: a FAIR description of observables based on the I-ADOPT Framework using semantic concepts.

API specification

It is not defined yet.

FAIR Principles coverage

I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

I-ADOPT can be used to describe variables in both the metadata and the data. This description is done using RDF (Resource Description Framework), a widely used language for knowledge representation.

I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

Concepts identified in the I-ADOPT ontology are represented following the FAIR principles, including the generation of PIDs for each concept.

I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

By decomposing the variable with the I-ADOPT object properties the description can be associated with the Property, the Object of Interest, the Matrix and Context Object. In this way, a variable concept is linked to a rich graph containing qualified references with specific descriptive roles.

R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Community standards were identified through the use of FIPs. The I-ADOPT service will support us in incorporating information about the scientific variables used within this community.

Metadata provided

measuredVariable

4.3 Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)

Description

The ORKG infrastructure mainly aims at providing a platform for representing research contributions as structured, interlinked data, as well as enabling their automated comparison.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service enables the production and publication of machine-readable scientific knowledge, published in academic literature. In the FAIR2Adapt project, the framework helps to FAIRify and synthesize scientific knowledge.

Input / Outputs

Input: article, software or data.

Output: it will be RO-Crates with structured (machine-readable) descriptions of scientific knowledge.

API specification

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

A complete specification of the API can be in ORKG REST API Documentation⁷.

FAIR Principles coverage

ORKG uses a FAIR-by-design model that provides locating and validating research outcomes. It satisfies F1 through persistent identifiers and I1 and I2 through structured JSON-LD vocabularies. The framework generates records to support the R1.2 requirement for data reuse.

Metadata provided

There are different metadata fields for each feature. Considering the system works as a graph, these fields are available as JSON-LD objects to help with machine-readability and integration.

4.4 ORKG Reborn

Description

The ORKG Reborn framework as an infrastructure shifting the emphasis to the pre-publication phase, which is designed to capture, curate, and publish analysis-ready scientific knowledge. The platform stores the main outcomes of research works as scientific statements, which encapsulate structured scientific statements together with their supporting evidence, including data, code, and computational workflows. These statements are linked to the evidence produced during data analysis in computational environments such as Python or R.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service provides features to facilitate the machine-supported retrieval, discovery, and synthesis of scientific knowledge. These services enable the publication of scientific claims that are linked to their supporting evidence (e.g., software, research variables, data) allowing synthesis researchers to verify and aggregate findings with high precision.

⁷ <https://tibhannover.gitlab.io/orkg/orkg-backend/api-doc>

Input / Outputs

Input:

Research submissions as file packages containing manuscripts, data, analysis code, and computational outputs (e.g., Python or R environments).

Output : The output of the system includes statements records containing machine-actionable scientific statements linked to supporting evidence, RO-Crate metadata packages describing each record, and JSON-LD representations of scientific statements generated via Dtreg⁸.

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be in API Documentation⁹.

FAIR Principles coverage

The ORKG Reborn framework provides Interoperability and Reusability by linking scientific statements to their supporting evidence. In addition to Findability and Accessibility, achieved by considering every research contribution and its fine-grained statements as distinct digital components, the framework covers the following FAIR principles:

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation The system uses JSON-LD and RO-Crate, which are formal and applicable standards for representing machine-readable knowledge.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles It employs vocabularies and data types registered with Data Type Registries (DTR).

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data Reborn statements reference supporting evidence using typed relationships that define the role of each component.

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes Scientific statements capture research outcomes related to their contextual evidence, including data analysis implementations that enable informed reuse.

⁸ <https://pypi.org/project/dtreg/>

⁹ https://FAIR2Adapt.github.io/knowledge-services/services/api_specification/T_4_2_swagger_ui.html

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R1.2. (Meta)data is associated with detailed provenance The framework generates provenance records, documenting the transition.

Also, Findability and Accessibility are addressed:

F1. (Meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers Both Reborn articles and individual scientific statements would have assigned unique DOIs.

F2. Data are described with rich metadata Records are richly described via the RO-Crate standard.

Metadata provided

RO-Crate metadata files and JSON-LD objects available for both interactive viewing within the ORKG infrastructure and for bulk download.

4.5 JackDAw AI LLM model integrating Geographical Information services

Description

This service implements an AI-driven interface and metadata engine to support FAIR data access and integration, enabling users to easily discover, select, and connect to relevant data sources through natural language both for non-technical and expert users. The JackDAw LLM can be either used for mapping metadata to standards such as ISO 19115, DCAT, and STAC or combined with a robust metadata ecosystem supporting natural language querying, contextual metadata selection, and dynamic mapping generation.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

The service can facilitate metadata extraction through natural language querying, field mapping, and eventually adaptive metadata generation. The service bridges the gap between raw or legacy data and FAIR principles, supporting data discovery, interoperability, and reuse across systems.

Input / Outputs

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Input: user submits a natural language query (e.g., “What crops are optimal for clay soils under drought conditions?”).

Output: the LLM interprets the user’s intent, identifies relevant metadata schemas, the results are then synthesized and enriched with provenance, usage notes and confidence levels. The result is presented to the user in a structured form with explanations. Output formats that can be implemented are JSON, GeoJSON, RDF, HTML.

API specification

Not available yet.

FAIR Principles coverage

The service covers the following FAIR principles¹⁰:

F2. Data are described with rich metadata

The service performs metadata extraction, semantic enrichment, and mapping to established schemas (ISO 19115, DCAT, STAC).

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

JackDAw LLM enables natural language search and automated metadata-based discovery of data sources.

I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

Supported through output formats JSON, GeoJSON, RDF.

I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

The service maps metadata to community schemas (ISO 19115, DCAT, STAC) and enriches metadata semantically using ontologies.

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

JackDAw LLM adds provenance, usage notes, confidence levels and semantic enrichment.

R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

The service explicitly generates provenance information.

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

The service aligns metadata with ISO 19115, DCAT, STAC.

¹⁰ GO FAIR. FAIR Principles. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Metadata provided

The system returns query results using a metadata model based on the query context and with annotations.

4.6 Metadata catalogue for geospatial data

Description

The geospatial data produced in Case Study 1 (Arctic Radioisotopes), Case Study 2 (RioMar project) and Case Study 3 (Hamburg) will be made available through a wrapper that provides unified access to different geospatial catalogues, enabling interoperable discovery and access regardless of the underlying infrastructure. Case Studies 1 and 2 use STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog), while Case Study 3 uses OGC standards. The metadata will be specifically used for visualisation of the geospatial datasets in these case studies using the Hub4Everybody platform developed and provided by Plan4All and Lesprojekt.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

The metadata catalogue for geospatial data acts as the discovery and access index for FAIRified geospatial resources. It is integrated via a wrapper so that the datasets (and, where relevant, services and endpoints) generated during FAIRification can be registered, searched, and referenced consistently—supporting discovery and reuse especially in Case Study 1 (Arctic Radioisotopes), Case Study 2 (RioMar) and Case Study 3 (Hamburg). It connects FDOs to geospatial distributions (files and/or OGC services), enabling users and machines to find, inspect, and access the right dataset version, with clear constraints for restricted data (metadata-only publication where needed).

Input / Output

Inputs:

Case Study 1 (Arctic Radioisotopes) and Case Study 2 (RioMar): FAIRified metadata prepared for publication in STAC catalogue, dataset descriptors and references for the pilot datasets, access links to the FAIR packages and published data distributions, indexing fields.

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Case Study 3 (Hamburg): Metadata records for risk maps and indices, geospatial layers, uploaded files, access links via WMS, WFS or OGC API, and metadata-only records for data that cannot be openly shared, links to RO-Crates, so the catalogue entry is connected to the full workflow context.

Outputs:

Case Study 1 (Arctic Radioisotopes) and Case Study 2 (RiOMar): a STAC catalogue that is searchable with machine-readable records, links to the corresponding RO-Crates, data files and basic metadata (space, time, keywords). The catalogue records can be used for visualisation and further workflows if needed.

Case Study 3 (Hamburg): Searchable catalogue entries (pointers to WMS, WFS, or OGC API endpoints, links to RO-Crates) in the Hub4Everybody platform; catalogue records that support direct map viewing (open from ROHub into Hub4Everybody) via stored visualization links and endpoints; persistent discovery of both open outputs and restricted inputs (metadata-only) to enable reuse planning and workflow transfer to other cities (e.g., Bremen) even without privileged data access.

API specification

Not available yet.

FAIR Principles coverage

F2. Data are described with rich metadata

The catalogue stores rich geospatial metadata enabling meaningful discovery and interpretation.

F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

Catalogue records explicitly link to the dataset distributions (files or service endpoints) and to the associated RO-Crate.

F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

The catalogue is the searchable resource enabling discovery across datasets, layers, and workflow outputs.

A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol

Catalogue records are retrievable via web APIs and protocols; distributions are provided via standard web and OGC endpoints where applicable.

A1.1. The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

Use of web standards and open geospatial service standards (e.g., OGC interfaces) supports broad interoperability.

A2. Metadata remain accessible even when the data are no longer available

Particularly important for Hamburg restricted datasets: metadata-only records document closed inputs even if data cannot be accessed openly.

I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

Catalogue records include qualified links to RO-Crates, publications, workflows, and related datasets (e.g., “isDerivedFrom”, “documents”, “hasServiceDistribution”).

R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

The catalogue maintains reuse-critical attributes, e.g., context, scope, processing level, blur and aggregation statements, etc.

R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

Catalogue records capture licensing and access constraints including internal or restricted terms where relevant.

R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

Records link to workflow context and provenance packaged in RO-Crates.

R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

4.7 FIP Wizard

Description

Within the FAIRification framework, the FIP Wizard captures FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) by means of a questionnaire that requires them to provide answers that explicitly profile the FAIR implementation approach of that community. FIPs are published by the FIP Wizard as FAIR (machine-readable) and Open data (nanopublications), which can then serve as a reference for practical FAIR data stewardship activities conducted by members of that community. FIP publication also encourages FIP reuse and repurposing by other communities, which saves time “reinventing the wheel” and simultaneously drives convergence on FAIR implementation choices. FIPs and used FAIR Supporting Resources can be searched in FAIR CONNECT.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service will assess the available and planned FAIR Supporting Resources to FAIRify digital objects.

It will be used to identify the FAIRness requirements of the community.

Input / Outputs

Input: N/A. It is based on smart forms answered by users.

Output: nanopublications for FIPs and FERs (FAIR Enable Resources), JSON,

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be found [here](#) and [here](#)

FAIR Principles coverage

A FIP covers the principle R1.3, as it specifies standards as agreed by a community of practice.

Metadata provided

4.8 Metadata extraction

Description

This service extracts metadata from text. It accepts input files in several formats, including Word documents (.doc, .docx), PowerPoint presentations (.pptx), PDF documents, and plain text files (.txt).

Topics

Topics categorize the text according to defined taxonomies, offering multiple perspectives on the analyzed content. Supported taxonomies include:

- Expert.ai Knowledge Graph Domains, extended with Earth and Environmental Sciences vocabulary.
- IPTC Media Topics, a three-level media-focused taxonomy.
- Fields of Research, which classify content into standardized academic disciplines and sub-disciplines used to organize and compare research activity across institutions and countries..
- NASA Scope and Subject taxonomy, it is used for classifying scientific and technical information, and contains 11 categories and 88 subcategories.

Key Entities

These fields capture the primary elements of the text at different levels of granularity, summarizing and condensing the content into essential terms. Extracted elements include main sentences, main lemmas, main phrases, and main concepts.

Entities

This section extracts entities referenced in the text, also at various levels of granularity. These may include:

- Organizations
- Locations
- Time references (dates, time ranges, days of the week, months, seasons, etc.)

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- People
- Data cubes (data cube identifiers found in the text)

Role in the FAIRification Framework

It will be used to generate machine-readable metadata to improve the FAIRness of Digital Objects.

Input / Outputs

Input: text (size to be defined)

Output: metadata including topics, keywords, entities, time, magnitudes, and categories in JSON-LD format compatible to ro-crate.

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be found [here](#).

FAIR Principles coverage

F2: data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

This enrichment service will extract relevant information from publications such as keywords, topics, geographical information, etc. This information will complete the metadata existing.

4.9 Scientific claims extraction and verification

Description

This service extracts claims from an input text and verifies them against scientific knowledge bases such as ORKG, OpenAIRE, S2ORC, and PubMed. It is based on the SciClaims system [6], which identifies claims in biomedical text, retrieves supporting evidence from PubMed, and assesses their veracity. While SciClaims focuses on biomedical claim analysis, this service will be adapted to the climate-adaptation domain.

The SciClaims system architecture is built around a Llama-3 8B Instruct model and an Elasticsearch-based retrieval engine. It processes biomedical or scientific text and produces

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a list of extracted claims, their verification status, relevant evidence, and a natural-language rationale. The model is deployed with vLLM, enabling high-throughput inference.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

It will be used to generate machine-readable metadata to improve the FAIRness of Digital Objects.

Input / Outputs

Input: text (size to be defined)

Output: Extracted claims and their provenance.

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be found [here](#).

FAIR Principles coverage

F2: data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

This enrichment service will extract relevant information from publications such as claims. This information will complete the metadata existing.

4.10 Pythia Question Answering Engine

Description

Pythia¹¹ is a knowledge graph agnostic question answering engine that facilitates natural language interaction with RDF data. It functions by translating user requests into semantically equivalent SPARQL queries which are subsequently executed on a target KG. It can function as a stand-alone tool or be used by an LLM-powered agent as an information retriever for knowledge graph resources.

¹¹ <https://github.com/SKefalidis/Pythia>

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It follows a pipeline architecture that follows the “plan-explore-generate” paradigm. It can be deployed over arbitrary knowledge graphs and is highly resilient to changes in the target ontology or the addition of new information in the knowledge graph.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

This service provides natural language query answering over any available knowledge graph.

It will improve findability and accessibility to the ROHub knowledge graph.

Input / Outputs

Input: text (natural language question)

Output: results of the final, executable query in one of the standard RDF result formats as well as the query itself

API specification

Not available yet.

FAIR Principles coverage

F1: Produced queries are logged and assigned unique identifiers, searchable through the service to enable discoverability and explainability of results.

F2: Query logs contain detailed information about the Text-to-SPARQL process that resulted in the generation of a particular query.

F3: Necessary for linking F1 and F2.

A1: Both service functionality and metadata are made available through APIs using standard protocols. APIs support authentication and authorization.

Metadata provided

Query logs that provide detailed documentation about the question answering process.

4.11 ToposKG

Description

ToposKG[7] is a complete system for generating geospatial knowledge graphs and enhancing existing ones with geospatial information. Through the use of the Topos methodology and accompanying tooling, RDF data are interlinked with a set of curated geospatial data to produce geospatially enriched knowledge graphs. Geospatial data are provided in a highly modular fashion and are both highly detailed and have a high degree of topological consistency. Additional functionalities provided by the Topos methodology and accompanying toolkit include translation of geo-entities and geospatial relation materialization to ensure near instant querying times.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

ToposKG provides a simple methodology and the appropriate tooling to enrich any knowledge graph with spatial information.

Input / Outputs

Input: RDF or Semi-structured data

Output: Geospatially enhanced RDF data

API specification

Not available yet.

FAIR Principles coverage

F2: Each geospatial entity is enriched with detailed metadata, including geometry type, provenance, source dataset, hierarchical relations, and multilingual labels.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

F3: Metadata records explicitly reference the IRIs of the geospatial entities they describe, enabling automated alignment between descriptive information and geometries.

F4: The full knowledge graph and its metadata are registered in a public SPARQL endpoint and GitHub repository, making them searchable and indexable by external services.

A1: ToposKG and its metadata can be retrieved via standard Linked Data protocols through the publicly hosted SPARQL endpoint and downloadable RDF dumps. Access is provided over open, universally implementable web standards (HTTPS, SPARQL 1.1). When needed, programmatic access to toolchain components (e.g., interlinking pipelines) is available through authenticated APIs in the Python library.

A2: Metadata describing all included datasets remain accessible through the SPARQL endpoint and GitHub, even if some source datasets change or become unavailable.

I2: The knowledge graph incorporates vocabularies that follow FAIR principles, including GeoSPARQL, standard administrative division ontologies, and community-adopted geospatial schemas.

R1: Each entity is richly described with attributes such as geometry accuracy, hierarchical structure, data source, translation status, and interlinking confidence scores. Additionally, the knowledge graph adheres to community standards for geospatial data representation (GeoSPARQL, RDF, Linked Data principles), ensuring compatibility with GIS and Semantic Web tools.

Metadata provided

GeoSPARQL query logs targeting the publicly available ToposKG endpoint, alongside metadata available for each unique data source available in ToposKG.

4.12 ROHub

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

Description

ROHub is an EOSC research enabling service supporting researchers in the adoption of FAIR and Open Science principles. It provides a holistic solution for the storage, lifecycle management, publishing and preservation of scientific investigations and campaigns via RO-Crate research objects (FDOs), in line with FAIR principles. ROHub leverages and integrates several research object added value services and EOSC services to deliver a comprehensive virtual research environment.

Role in the FAIRification Framework

ROHub will be the default repository for FAIR Digital Objects in the project. It will integrate the FDOs created in other platforms such as ORKG or LOOM. Researchers will be able to modify the metadata of their FDOs in this platform.

Input / Outputs

Input: Through its graphical interface, python library and API, users can create and modify FDOs. This information will be consistent with the RO-Crate profiles that will be generated in the project.

Output: Researchers will be able to download their FDOs in multiple formats, such as ZIP files or an RO-Crate metadata file.

API specification

A specification of the API can be found here¹².

FAIR Principles coverage

F1, F2 (partially), F3, F4, A1.1, A1.2, I1, I2, I3, R1.1, R1.2, R1.3

¹² [Welcome to ROHUB-API's documentation! — ROHUB-API v1.2.1 documentation](#)

F1: (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.

This service can be used to generate global persistent identifiers. So if you can generate a persistent identifier, the publication should be uploaded to Rohub, as part of a Research Object. The persistent identifier is generated using the service provided by w3id.org.

F2: data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)

The F2 principle is partially covered because it is very dependent on the users. Nevertheless, ROHub will implement the RO-Crate profiles, which will contain the metadata relevant for the specific community.

F3: metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe

The service ROHub generates metadata automatically once you upload a resource to the platform, so there is no need for human intervention. The link is visible in the graphic interface and as a metadata in the RO-Crate.

A1.1: the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable

Https protocol is open, free, and universally implementable. It means that the use of both platforms assure the achievement of this principle.

A1.2: the protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary

The protocol https allows the authentication of users by using the header Authentication.

I1: (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation

ROHub can manage RO-Crates to describe the research objects, so the metadata is described using a specification for knowledge representation.

I2: (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles

ROHub through the use of RO-Crates profiles is able to manage FAIR vocabularies by default. It is also applied to the data because users can semantically annotate the resources present in the Research Object.

I3: (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

This FAIR principle can be achieved automatically by using this service since they are able to export the data using ROCrate.

R1.1: (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license

ROHub provides mechanisms to add licenses (with the appropriate links) to the digital objects.

R1.2: (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance

ROcrate contains some properties, based on the types CreateAction and UpdateAction from schema.org to represent the provenance. ROHub allows users to specify these properties in their system, covering the application of this principle.

R1.3: (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

The main community standards will be identified by FIPS (see D5.1). These standards will be incorporated as RoCrate profiles, and these will be integrated into ROHub.

Metadata provided

Ro-Crate profiles

4.13 DeSci Publish

Role in the FAIRification Framework

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

DeSci Publish is a pre-print and publication platform built using Content Identifiers (CIDs) through the Inter-Planetary File System (IPFS). This system gives all Research Objects truly persistent identifiers version control, an Automatically Generated RO Crate, and AI knowledge enhancement + search for Research Objects.

This service can currently make it easier for researchers to ensure their public research object metadata is in line with FAIR principles. It has the capability to provide RO Crates and limited metadata for private data, or to act as a public or private gateway to data hosted on local servers.

Input / Outputs

Input: any research artifact or file type

Output: a research object with a dPID, RO Crate, and AI analysis.

API specification

A complete specification of the API can be found [here](#).

FAIR Principles coverage

F1 - (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers

It assigns persistent identifiers using the dPID protocol which allows for fine-grained identifiers for each research artifact down to a data point. It also assigns DOI's for the Research Object as a whole.

F3 - (Meta) data clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.

A tool called “RO Crate Transformer” implements RO Crate standards and includes the dPID + DOI of the research object, and the CIDs of every research artifact within the research object.

F4 - (Meta) data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.

RO-Crates generated in DeSci Publish are indexed both on Google Scholar and on the InterPlanetary Network Indexer.

A 1.1 - The protocol is open, free and universally implementable.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

Both HTTPS and IPFS are open protocols.

I1 - (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

RO Crates generated by DeSci Publish are in line with RDF and JSON-LD Standards.

I2 - (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.

chema.org vocabularies are used through RO Crate.

R1.1 - (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license.

License attribution is requested from the authors upon upload and associated with the (meta)data.

R1.2 - (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.

All (meta)data are associated with upload information and version control. Provenance prior to upload is not tracked by the platform.

Metadata

Title, Authors, Keywords, and Abstract are extracted directly from the text. The Open Alex API is then used to assign ORCID IDs to authors and match keywords to topics. Additionally, the platform discovers related papers and identifies qualified reviewers.

5. Application of the Framework: Initial Showcases and Next Steps

This section of the deliverable describes how the FAIRification Framework and the methodology presented previously are applied in each case study. The objective is to analyze the adaptability of the methodology and the framework across the different scenarios addressed in the project. Each case study is associated with a FAIRification Plan (FP), which describes the steps required to FAIRify the Digital Objects and the services involved in the process. These FAIRification Plans will be implemented as FAIRification pipelines in further developments, to automate the process as much as possible. The list of Digital Objects to be FAIRified was identified in Deliverable D5.2 on requirements elicitation.

5.1 Introduction

During the requirements elicitation process (see Deliverable D5.2), we identified that the Digital Objects involved fall into three specific categories: data, software, and publications.

Since most resources within each category share common characteristics, we decided to prepare FAIRification Plan (FP) templates for each category. The FAIRification Plan of each case study will then be developed by adapting the relevant template(s) to the specific context of the case study.

In the following, we present the templates for each category.

Data

There is a wide diversity of data managed across the case studies, ranging from sensor data and simulation outputs to time-series and socio-economic data. These data may be available in external repositories, or they may be stored by researchers in internal infrastructures. Consequently, an explicit archiving phase is required as part of the FAIRification process.

To support data archiving, FAIR2Adapt can rely on the following infrastructure options:

- For small datasets (less than 1 GB), ROHub can be used to preserve and manage the data.
- For medium-sized datasets (from 1 GB up to 10 GB), FAIR2Adapt can use the EGI DataHub for data preservation. This service is integrated with ROHub.
- For large datasets (from 10 GB up to 50 GB), Zenodo can be used as an appropriate option.
- Finally, for very large datasets, FAIR2Adapt will rely on external repositories, which will be integrated into the FAIRification Framework.

The figure 11 below depicts a generic FAIRification Plan for data.

Fig 11. Data FP template

The objective of this FAIRification Plan is to FAIRify both the input data and the output data (results). In this case, Zenodo has been selected as the archival system; however, additional systems may be used depending on the specific data requirements. A persistent identifier will be generated and used in ROHub to integrate the data into the FAIR Digital Object (FDO).

The enrichment process will be supported by two services: **I-ADOPT** and the **Mapper**. With the support of the I-ADOPT service, the variables present in the data will be semantically described and incorporated into the ROHub record, once the integration of the service into ROHub has been completed.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

The Mapper is an internal component of the FAIRification Framework whose objective is to transform the metadata schema of the input and output data into the appropriate RO-Crate profile, using mappings defined in SSSOM¹³ (see an example of mappings in M2.1). The diagram indicates the involvement of a researcher, as not all metadata required by the RO-Crate profile are available in Zenodo. Consequently, researcher intervention is needed to complete the RO-Crate metadata.

Once all metadata have been created and validated, the final step is to publish the complete set of information on the ROHub platform, resulting in the generation of an FDO.

Software

The following FP will be applied to FAIRify source code that normally in the CS is used to execute large models in HPC to small scripts. The objective of this FAIRification is to favour its reuse and reproducibility.

The recommendations from the EVERSE¹⁴ project will be followed to ensure its FAIR compliance. These recommendations can be summarised as follows:

- Include a README file to support the FAIRification process and improve the reproducibility of the resources. A specific README template will be provided for FAIR2Adapt. More details are available in the EVERSE guidelines¹⁵. A template¹⁶ has been created to facilitate the process.
- Add a `codemeta.json` file. FAIR2Adapt users can use the *autocodemeta*¹⁷ generator to produce an initial version of this file, then edit the automatically detected values. Once completed, the file can be uploaded to the repository.
- Add a citation file to the repository, following the recommendations from EVERSE¹⁸. A Github action will be created to automatically generate a CITATION file based on the `codemeta.json`
- Once all required information has been added, the repository can be linked to Zenodo. Zenodo integrates with GitHub and automatically archives the source code whenever a release is created.
- Create a release in the GitHub repository. This will trigger the deposition of the source code in Zenodo.

The following figure 12 depicts the whole process.

¹³ <https://github.com/mapping-commons/SSSOM>

¹⁴ [RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit](#)

¹⁵ [tasks: Creating a good README | RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit](#)

¹⁶ https://github.com/FAIR2Adapt/fairification-framework/blob/main/templates/README_template.md

¹⁷ <http://autocodemeta.linkeddata.es/>

¹⁸ [tasks: Citing software | RSQKit: Research Software Quality Kit](#)

Fig 12. Data FP template

Publication

Another type of digital object that we aim to FAIRify is scientific publications. These are typically available in journal repositories; however, the objective of this FAIRification Plan is to create a FAIR Digital Object (FDO) associated with each publication, together with its corresponding metadata. The goal is to transform a publication into a machine-actionable resource, and the core service used to achieve this is the ORKG Reborn service.

The following figure depicts the whole process.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

Fig 13. Publication FP template

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

The starting point of the process is a PDF file, which is available in a journal repository. Two main enrichment services will be used to (i) extract the following metadata fields from the publication: topics, keywords, entities, temporal information, magnitudes, and categories; and (ii) extract scientific claims.

All extracted metadata will be ingested into the ORKG Reborn service, creating a structured record for the publication within the platform. The diagram highlights the involvement of a researcher, as the researcher can use ORKG Reborn to validate the information extracted by the enrichment services and to complement the record with additional information where needed.

Once the record is completed, it will be exported to the ROHub platform using the appropriate RO-Crate profile.

5.2 Application to Case Studies

This section describes how the different FAIRification Plans are applied to the case studies, identifying the relevant services used, the associated showcases, and potential dependencies.

Before presenting the description of each case study, we briefly introduce the different showcases proposed in the project to illustrate the potential of FAIRifying resources across the case studies. A more detailed description of these showcases can be found in Deliverable D1.3.

1. **SC1:** Data processing pipeline for coastal water quality modelling. The purpose is to enable regriding of simulation output to another grid (DGGS-Healpix), FAIRify it, and integrate in a STAC catalogue—overcoming the limited accessibility and usability of model data. It is related to CS2.
2. **SC2:** FAIR GIS workflow for urban climate risk assessment. The purpose is to FAIRify the software (GIS pipeline to generate the risk assessment maps) to create a workflow that can easily be reused in CS6 for the City of Bremen and/or transfer cases to produce risk maps—demonstrating cross-case replicability. It is related to CS3 Hamburg.
3. **SC3:** Knowledge production from scientific publication. The purpose is to make scientific claims and workflows verifiable and reusable for other researchers who wish to reuse knowledge or build upon similar methods. It is related to CS3
4. **SC4:** Literature review and extraction pipeline. The purpose is to compare manual vs. LLM-based extraction and create machine-readable systematic reviews using the TIB Knowledge Loom outcomes uploaded to weAdapt to benefit the global adaptation community. It is related to CS4 and CS5.

5.2.1 Case Study 1: Arctic Radioisotopes

Vision

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

This case study aims to help stakeholders understand how climate change may affect radionuclide distribution in the Arctic, with implications for public and environmental safety. It does so by analysing climate projections produced by the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM) under defined scenarios and assessing how resulting changes in radionuclide patterns may influence exposure levels for local populations.

Digital Objects

During the requirements elicitation process described in Deliverable D5.2, the digital objects identified correspond to simulation data, sensor data, and time series data. Also, the model needs to be FAIRified.

FAIRification Plan considerations

The data are not currently archived in any repository, and some of the datasets are very large (around 200 GB). As a result, the main challenge is to identify a suitable repository in which to store them, as common services such as ROHub, Zenodo, or EGI DataHub cannot be used by volume limitation.

The selected option is the Norwegian Research Data Archive (NIRD), which supports very large volumes of data. NIRD is based on CKAN, can generate DOIs for data collections, and allows the export of metadata as RO-Crates. This makes it compatible with the project's publishing services, such as ROHub, ORKG, and the DeSci Publisher.

Once the datasets are archived, the RO-Crate will be exported from NIRD to ROHub, where the FDO will be enriched using the project's enrichment services. An additional service or component is required to transform the RO-Crate profile used by NIRD into the FAIR2Adapt RO-Crate profile.

The model involved in the CS will be FAIRified following the plan established in the FP Software template. For it, the source code will be uploaded to a Github repository created by the researchers.

Services involved

The main services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the Software FAIRification Plan template.

We expect to include the Metadata Catalogue for Geospatial Data (see 4.6) to register the results in a STAC catalogue that is searchable with machine-readable records, links to the corresponding RO-Crates, data files and basic metadata (space, time, keywords). The catalogue records can be used for visualisation and further workflows if needed.

5.2.2 Case Study 2: Biscayan RiOMar

Vision

This case study aims to assess coastal water quality and marine ecosystem health in France while anticipating climate impacts expected by the end of the century. Using high-resolution outputs from the RiOMar model, it seeks to identify risks and vulnerabilities that can inform scientifically grounded climate-change adaptation strategies for coastal regions.

Description

Local stakeholders—such as oyster farmers facing growing climate-related threats—need accessible, actionable information, yet they struggle to use RiOMar data due to its volume and complexity. Challenges include determining which indicators best represent ecosystem vulnerability and navigating data and resources that are often not available in French, limiting effective decision-making and adaptation planning.

FAIRification Plan considerations

In this case study, the FAIRification process will focus on both data and a model (software) in order to enable the reproduction of an experiment on a different grid.

For the data, the plan is to use the EGI DataHub service instead of Zenodo, which is the default option defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template.

One open question related to the model in this case study will be addressed in the coming months in the SC2. Although the source code of the model will be FAIRified, the model must be executed in a high-performance computing (HPC) environment due to its computational requirements. This will require additional FAIRification steps, as the execution workflow (i.e. the recipe required to run the model) will also need to be FAIRified. The use of platforms such as WorkflowHub¹⁹ is currently being considered to support this process.

Services involved

The main services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the Software FAIRification Plan template.

We expect the use of additional services to share the workflows in HPC systems.

5.2.3 Case Study 3: City of Hamburg

Vision

Hamburg faces diverse climate-induced stressors, making systematic and cross-sectoral adaptation essential. This vision focuses on assessing how climate hazards affect urban societies by integrating socio-economic vulnerability and exposure data with physical climate

¹⁹ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

hazard information. Effective adaptation also requires strong coordination among public authorities, administration and research.

Description

At the city scale, developing meaningful adaptation strategies depends on high-resolution, granular data that spans infrastructure, population characteristics, environmental conditions, and climate stressors. In Hamburg such data is publicly available on the geodata platform “Geoportal Hamburg” provided by the city of Hamburg, where data is collected from various city authorities and organisations. Nonetheless, data is not always up-to-date, and is not linked to European or global platforms like Copernicus. While the Geoportal Hamburg aggregates 572 datasets with metadata and maps, it is only referenced in Climate-ADAPT in terms of qualitative information impeding Europe-wide data sharing and informed climate-risk assessment. Furthermore, different cities use various data formats making it difficult to transfer risk assessment practices from one city to another. Coordinated data curation, integration, and accessibility are therefore critical to understanding future climate risks and supporting informed, effective adaptation planning.

FAIRification Plan considerations

The FAIRification process for this case study will focus on applying FAIR principles to a recent study carried out using state of the art algorithms. The publication will be transformed into a machine-readable format, improving the findability of its resources and enabling their reuse by other services. Together, the publication, software, and data will be FAIRified in order to increase their reproducibility and facilitate their application in other cities, such as Bremen. For this purpose, we will have to apply the three FP templates proposed in 5.1

The following figure depicts an overall picture of the three FP templates for this case of study. The FDO generated will contain the data, the publication and the software needed to reproduce the experiment, and to replicate in other cities.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

Fig 14. Overview of the CS3 FAIRification Plan

For this CS, a Galaxy Engine will be required to execute the model. For this reason, a Galaxy recipe will need to be created and FAIRified in order to enable the execution of the model in other cities, such as Bremen, as planned in SC3.

Services involved

The services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the FAIRification Plan templates.

Additionally, access to a Galaxy Engine will be integrated to enable workflow sharing.

As we commented in CS2, the metadata catalogue can be used to register the results using the Hub4Everybody platform. Visualizations links can be integrated in ROHub, allowing users to view geospatial outputs directly from the FDO interface.

5.2.4 Case Study 4: Designing a FAIR National Adaptation Hub

Vision

This case study aims to develop FAIR and open data resources to support the creation of national climate-adaptation hubs and to apply the FAIR2Adapt methodology in designing Portugal's first National Adaptation Hub. Its vision is to strengthen the data foundations needed for effective national-level adaptation planning.

Description

Countries face increasing pressure to enhance climate resilience and align with the EU's call for smarter and more systemic adaptation, yet the proliferation of portals and platforms has made it difficult for users to identify reliable and relevant information. The challenge lies in finding, extracting, curating and sharing diverse climate and non-climate data (e.g., projections, socio-economic and environmental datasets) to inform adaptation decisions across the entire planning cycle.

FAIRification Plan considerations

The objective of this plan is to establish a process for creating FDOs for the publications in the National Hub in order to:

- i) extract metadata from the publications, and
- ii) generate machine-actionable resources in ROHub.

We will follow the template proposed for FAIRifying publications in section 5.1

Once a publication is identified, the relevant sentences and metadata will be extracted using our enrichment services. This information will then be deposited into ORKG, a platform designed to represent scientific knowledge contained in publications.

Researchers will validate all extracted information in ORKG. After validation, the information will be exported to ROHub as RO-Crates.

Only the publications themselves will be FAIRified, excluding the associated data and software.

The following figure depicts the process.

Fig 15. Overview of the CS4 FAIRification Plan

Additionally, one of the requirements identified in D5.2 is the FAIRification of databases, such as the Portal of Clima²⁰. To automatize the process, an extra component will be developed in the framework to automatically generate the FDOs from the resources of a repository. This will be tested in SC4.

Services involved

The services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the FAIRification Plan template for publication.

²⁰ <https://w3id.org/gff/rao/terms/Database>

5.2.5 Case Study 5: Enriching weADAPT and the Connectivity Hub Global

Vision

This case study aims to enhance weADAPT so that communities, planners, researchers, and policymakers can more easily access and share climate-resilient adaptation knowledge. By breaking down information silos and connecting existing resources across portals and publications, it seeks to reduce redundancy, promote collaboration, and ensure that adaptation knowledge becomes accessible through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Description

Current challenges stem from fragmented, unstructured, and difficult-to-find information, which limits communication and coordinated action. The project addresses this by improving taxonomies and developing knowledge graphs to make climate-related data, case studies, socio-economic scenarios, and adaptation measures more discoverable and usable. Through systematic extraction and curation of climate and non-climate information, it aims to strengthen adaptation planning across all levels.

FAIRification Plan considerations

This plan is very similar to the plan proposed for CS4. In this case, the platform wants to improve the metadata associated with the publication, as well as to create FDOs to integrate it in ROHub in order to improve their findability. There is no interest in identifying the data and software associated with publications.

After the requirements elicitation phase, a new pipeline was suggested by the community. WeAdapt is working on a controlled vocabulary for its community, so they are interested in sharing with other communities. This vocabulary can be found here²¹. In order to FAIRify it, we will use the methodology LOT4FAIR [8].

Services involved

The services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the FAIRification Plan template for publication.

5.2.6 Case Study 6: FAIRification of a Climate Adaptation Strategy

Vision

²¹ <https://connectivity-hub.com/terms>

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

This case study aims to improve the accessibility, usability, and clarity of a climate adaptation strategy by applying FAIR principles to both the policy document and its underlying climate-risk and adaptation data. It also seeks to strengthen science-policy communication by ensuring that information is clearly structured, well-documented, and actionable for policymakers and stakeholders.

Description

Climate adaptation strategies are vital reference tools, yet they are often difficult to find, interpret, or reuse due to inconsistent formats and limited metadata. By applying FAIR principles and enhancing communication practices, the project works to make these strategies and their datasets more accessible and update-ready. A key focus is understanding the needs of policymakers, city staff, and other data users to ensure the information can be effectively integrated into planning and decision-making processes.

FAIRification Plan considerations

The main DO involved in this CS are policy documents and data about temperature and precipitations, including maps and time-series data.

As in another CS, we will follow the templates provided in 5.1 to FAIRify publications and data. In this case, the data is available in PDFs in the Data Portal of Bremen²². This poses a challenge, as the data must first be extracted from the PDFs in order to be FAIRified. We will explore the application of AI models to extract table content from PDFs and data from visualizations.

Services involved

The services involved in this case study are those defined in the Data FAIRification Plan template and the FAIRification Plan template for publication and data.

As we can see in the considerations, we will need some extra services to extract the data from the PDFs available in the Bremen Data Portal. We will explore its integration in other FAIR2Adapt services such as ORKG Reborn and ROHub.

²² <https://www.klimaanpassung.bremen.de/>

6. Conclusions and next steps

In this deliverable, we present the FAIR2Adapt Framework, an ecosystem of services and resources designed to FAIRify the digital resources of the Climate Adaptation community. The framework defines a structured methodology for building FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) based on community requirements, covering the identification of the Digital Objects (DOs), to be FAIRified and the definition of FAIRification Plans that specify the sequence of steps required to create FDOs.

With the support of the services integrated within FAIR2Adapt, the framework aims to automate the FAIRification process as much as possible through the creation of FAIRification pipelines, an implementation of a FAIRification Plan. This approach reduces human intervention while increasing the scalability and efficiency of FAIRification activities. The services include components for enriching, publishing, and managing FDOs, as well as for supporting the FAIRification process as a whole. Many of these services are generic and therefore have the potential to be reused by other communities beyond the climate adaptation domain.

As part of the framework, we have designed generic FAIRification Plan templates for each category of digital objects (data, software, and publications). These templates serve as reusable building blocks for constructing the FAIRification Plan of each case study. This approach promotes modularity and reuse, while still allowing the plans to be adapted to the specific characteristics and requirements of each case study.

To further support reuse and replication across case studies, a collection of showcases has been defined. A recurrent and representative scenario is the FAIRification of scientific publications together with their supplementary materials, such as datasets and software. This approach aims to improve the reproducibility of scientific results and their replication in other contexts. In this scenario, platforms such as ORKG, together with services for metadata and knowledge extraction from publications, play a key role in simplifying the FAIRification process.

This deliverable also explores different approaches for representing FAIR Digital Objects and defines how these will be addressed within FAIR2Adapt. In particular, several RO-Crate profiles will be created to capture the metadata requirements of different communities, improving the findability and interoperability of FDOs. In addition, nanopublications will be used to further enrich FDOs with fine-grained, machine-actionable information derived from publications.

The FDOs generated within the project will be made accessible through the ROHub platform, which will act as the central environment for managing, publishing, and discovering FDOs. ROHub will also enable the aggregation and discovery of FDOs originating from other platforms, such as ORKG Reborn and DeSci Publish, ensuring a coherent and profile-based representation of all FDOs.

D3.1 – FAIRification Framework

The next steps of the FAIRification Framework will focus on its practical implementation and validation. In the coming months, FAIR2Adapt will develop demonstrators based on the defined showcases in order to test some of the FAIRification Plans (and pipelines) and collect feedback from the participating communities. This feedback will be used to improve the plans and pipelines, as well the services. The first release of the services in WP3 will be on M18. In addition, we plan to present the framework (plans, pipelines, and services) to our sister project, ClimateAdapt4EOSC, during its next General Assembly in February 2026, with the aim of establishing synergies between our FAIRification approaches.

Finally, the FAIR2Adapt Framework should not be considered a static outcome, but a dynamic and evolving resource. It has been designed following a modular and flexible approach to ensure that it can adapt over time to new requirements, services, and community practices.

7. References

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